

CULTURAL FUSION IN HIP-HOP: THE ROLE OF EUROPEAN PATTERNS IN THE AMERICAN MUSIC INDUSTRY

Abstract.

The purpose of the article. To reveal the features of European hip-hop culture in connection with its origin from the USA. **Research methodology.** The main scientific principles applied in the article are: historical-logical, historical-comparative, systematic, comprehensive and holistic, objective and genetic, etc. In the field of philosophy of culture, the following approaches occupy an important place: phenomenological, humanistic, cultural, anthropological, hermeneutic, semiotic, etc. Modern musicology studies the phenomena and processes inherent in musical culture and creativity; studies various aspects of performing skills, examines the specifics of perception, comprehension, interpretation, analysis and evaluation of a musical work. Comparative musicology studies the features of musical cultures of different countries of the world, in particular different musical systems, modes, scales, instruments, vocal and choreographic forms, considered in cultural-historical and anthropological aspects. Methods from the field of musical instrument science are also acceptable. Methods from musical aesthetics and semiotics are also important for application. The article also involved methods from the sociology of music, musical acoustics. **The scientific novelty of the study** lies in revealing the relationship between the creation of hip-hop culture in the USA and its spread and mutual influence in continental Europe. **Conclusions.** 1. Hip-hop culture was initiated in the USA. 2. Thanks to the international proclamation of its values by leading hip-hopers, this culture has spread, including in European territories. 3. Musical, social, cultural motifs and values developed by hip-hopers in Europe have a certain influence on the North American music industry, significantly expanding the boundaries of music and dance inherent in hip-hop culture, especially from the point of view of the development of hip-hop fusion genres and subgenres.

Keywords. Hip-hop, genre, subgenre, style, substyle, USA, continental Europe, music industry.

Justification for the Research Topic.

The relevance of the research is determined by contemporary processes that define the development of culture in general and musical culture in particular. It concerns hip-hop culture, which, having emerged in the 1970s in the USA, actively conquered the musical space, primarily in continental Europe. In turn, European hip-hop motifs, melodies, lyrics, and, overall, the values inherent in European musical culture have had and continue to have a certain influence on the development of the music industry in the USA. It also refers to hip-hop tours that have promoted and continue to promote a cultural and musical dialogue between North America and Western Europe.

It is also impossible to ignore the fact of the organization of hip-hop music festivals both in the USA and in continental Europe. Musicians, producers, technical personnel, and others exchange ideas and implement joint projects aimed at expanding the influence of hip-hop culture. They constantly modify technical and technological equipment, which allows them to significantly intensify both the process of musical creativity and the expansion of the socio-cultural niche of hip-hop from a business perspective.

Analysis of Previous Works.

Steven Hager (1951-) was the first to begin studying the hip-hop movement of the South Bronx. In 1984, St. Martin's Press published his groundbreaking book "Hip Hop: The Illustrated History of Break Dancing, Rap Music, and Graffiti." The first use of the term "hip-hop" in print, applied to characterize this culture and its elements, occurred in 1982 in an interview between Afrika Bambaataa and Michael Holman in *East Village Eye* (this cultural magazine was edited by Leonard Abrams; it was published from May 1979 to January 1987; it covered, among other things, the topic of hip-hop in New York's East Village during the 1980s) [Lawrence, Tim, 2016].

Music critic Peter Shapiro (1972-; club owner, concert promoter, director, magazine publisher, writer, and entrepreneur from New York) wrote that Kool Herc's innovations laid the foundation for hip-hop. He also noted that "another DJ, Grandwizard Theodore (1963-), contributed to its trademark flourishing in 1977/1978, namely through 'scratching'" [Shapiro, Peter, 2005].

In the book *In Search of Africa*, Manthia Diawara asserts that hip-hop is truly the voice of people marginalized in modern society. The author states:
"...The worldwide spread of hip-hop as a market revolution is actually a global expression of poor people's desire for a good life...this struggle corresponds to the nationalist struggle for citizenship and belonging..." [Diawara, Manthia, 2009].

Orlando Patterson (1940-) believes that the revitalization of hip-hop music will occur worldwide: this is linked to the fact that traditional cultural values are blending with American hip-hop [Patterson, Orlando, 2008].

Alexander Weheliye notes:
"...Popular music, typically in the form of recordings, continues to function as one of the principal channels of communication between different geographical and cultural moments in the African diaspora, allowing artists to articulate and realize their diasporic citizenship along with an international audience, [and to establish dialogue – Author] with other diasporas..." [Weheliye, Alexander, 2013].

In our view, this approach highlights the importance of the influence of European hip-hop on the US music industry through individuals of African descent who implemented hip-hop on the continent.

Among domestic researchers, we highlight two works. Oleksii Pastukhov, in his article [Pastukhov, 2024], cites Greg Dimitriadis (Professor of Educational Leadership and Policy, UB SUNY, USA), who recounts the history of the formation of hip-hop culture from the mid-1970s as an integrated series of community-based living practices, up to the point when it spread beyond the neighborhoods of New York [Dimitriadis G., 2009]. Pastukhov also referred to the article by Ukrainian researchers S. Kolesnyk and T. Volokh [Kolesnyk S., Volokh T., 2018], which paid significant attention to the origins, formation, and evolution of hip-hop culture as self-sufficient, full-fledged, and unique.

In 2014, Adriana N. Helbig (1974-; professor at the University of Pittsburgh, ethnomusicologist, researcher of Ukrainian, Romani, and African musical cultures) published a monograph in the USA [Adriana Helbig, 2014]. It is significant as an ethnographic study in

the field of musicology on Ukrainian hip-hop, tracing its origins in a past historical period to Ukraine. The author worked on this project from 2004 to 2010, made several visits to Ukraine, and undertook a two-month trip to Africa. In the foreword to this publication, she emphasized the role of hip-hop, historically associated with African American culture, and its significant influence on the civil rights movement, social development, the political situation, and global cultural processes worldwide.

Overall, we believe that the issue under study has not received sufficient attention in the domestic cultural and artistic space. It requires further elaboration. We hope that this work will make a certain contribution to the development of this research direction.

The purpose of the research.

To reveal the peculiarities of European hip-hop culture in connection with its origin in the United States; to analyze the process of interaction between hip-hop culture in the United States and continental Europe.

Presentation of the Main Part of the Research

Hip-hop culture is an artistic movement that emerged in New York City within the African American community [Hip-Hop Was Born in New York City, 1984, p. 10]. Hip-hop, as a type of art and culture, has been significantly influenced both by male artists and female performers [The Boston Globe, 1992, p. 52]. It incorporates in its musical forms the key elements of rap, DJing, turntables, and breakdancing [Brown, Lauren, 2009]. Other elements include graffiti, beatboxing, street entrepreneurship, hip-hop language, and hip-hop fashion [KRS-ONE – 9 Elements..., 2017].

Hip-hop represents both a new and old cultural phenomenon. The use of track, beat, and bassline sampling technology (from old recordings) for this art form means that a major part of this culture revolves around the idea of updating classical records, views, and experiences for a modern audience ["About"..., 2019]. At the same time, hip-hop music follows in the footsteps of earlier African American and Latino musical genres, such as blues, jazz, ragtime, funk, salsa, and disco. By 1979, hip-hop music had gained the status of a

mainstream cultural genre. It spread influentially around the world in the 1990s along with gangsta rap ["The History of Hip Hop Music" ..., 2017].

The group Chic played a major role in its establishment. They inspired The Sugarhill Gang to use their single "Good Times," which, in turn, became the foundation for the success of "Rapper's Delight" (1979), launching the musical format of hip-hop. At the end of 1979, Debbie Harry (Blondie) invited Nile Rodgers (Chic) to a hip-hop party where the main track was the break from Chic's song "Good Times" [*"The Story of Rapper's Delight by Nile Rodgers" ..., 2013]. Blondie's 1981 hit "Rapture" became the first major single with elements of hip-hop performed by a "white" band. Here is an excerpt that had a strong influence on the hip-hop audience in the United States: "...You eat Cadillacs, Lincolns, Mercuries, and Subarus, and you don't stop, you keep on eating cars. Then, when there are no more cars, you go out at night and eat up bars where people meet face to face, dance cheek to cheek, one to one, man to man..." In our opinion, it resonated with the African American hip-hop community in the sense of their participation in the social unrest that was taking place in the United States at the time, particularly regarding the clashes between the "white" majority and the African American minority.

Especially vulnerable in the sense of this confrontation were the lines:

"...Marco, Merrick, Terry Lee, Gary Tibbs, and your truly On the naughty North and in the sexy South We all sing... On the naughty North and in the sexy South We all sing..."

That is, in our opinion, it refers to the confrontation between the North and the South in the United States dating back to the time of the Civil War. It was then that people of African descent ceased to be slaves. We believe that this motif carries a certain ideological weight in the sense of the liberation of African American consciousness, who still today do not find themselves in a privileged position in social life in the United States, especially when it comes to life in the ghetto. It is here that African American hip-hop artists have the opportunity to widely unfold their deep consciousness, worldview motives, moods, and ideas.

On the other hand, the lyrics by Debbie Harry and the reference to Fab 5 Freddy (Fred Brathwaite, 1959–, American artist, director, and hip-hop pioneer; he gained wider recognition in 1981 when Debbie Harry mentioned him in Blondie's song "Rapture," singing: "Fab 5 Freddy told me everybody's fly"), as well as the participation of graffiti artists in the "Rapture" video, were a very early but sincere attempt to build bridges from English-speaking Europe to hip-hop culture in New York City. In our opinion, it was rather a manifestation of hipsterism in the center of Manhattan, trying to transition into the early hip-hop scene of the Bronx. It was precisely this transition that was voiced by the "white" New Wave band. Moreover, the track "Rapture" was sampled by American rappers for years afterwards. Be that as it may, as a result, this single took first place (!) on the American Billboard Hot 100 chart. Thus, the initial influence of continental hip-hop on the music industry in the United States was launched. Blondie's pioneering entry into rap was sincerely welcomed by the then-scene. Moreover, it contributed to opening up the new genre—hip-hop—to a wider audience.

The term "hip-hop" was first heard in the song "Rapper's Delight" performed by The Sugarhill Gang (1979): "*...I said a hip, hop, the hippie the hippie to the hip hip hop, and you don't stop*" [Larkin, Colin, 2015]. Lovebug Starski, a DJ from the Bronx who released the single "The Positive Life" (1981), and DJ Hollywood (1954–) began using this term, referring to new "disco-rap" music.

In 1982, A. Bambaataa and his followers, a group of dancers, artists, and DJs, going beyond the borders of the USA, organized the first hip-hop tour [Chang, Jeff, 2005, pp. 63, 89, 91, 94–101, 141, 170, 182–183]. In his conviction, hip-hop tours play the role of a "key," whose aim is to expand the influence of hip-hop and its Universal Zulu Nation. He considers peace, unity, love, and joyful youth leisure to be the key cultural values of hip-hop. In turn, his influence inspired many foreign artists, including the French rapper MC Solaar [Chang, Jeff, 2009]. In 1982, A. Bambaataa, inspired by the futuristic electronic music of the group Kraftwerk, debuted on the stage of New York's club The Roxy with the vinyl single "AEIOU Sometimes Y" by the pioneering group EBN-OZN [Fink, Robert, 2005]. After

mixing electro with hip-hop, his composition "Planet Rock" (1986) was born, which soon became very popular and widely known in the USA.

Throughout 1984, youth around the world were captivated by hip-hop culture. At that time, the art of hip-hop and the "slang" of American urban communities reached Europe: here, the global appeal of hip-hop culture was finally rooted. This effect was especially noticeable in the United Kingdom, where British hip-hop gained its own voice and style thanks to She Rockers, MC Duke, Derek B, Silver Bullet, Monie Love, Caveman, and London Posse.

Hip-hop from the USA was exported to the United Kingdom at the end of the 1970s. The establishment of British hip-hop began when the first recorded rap composition in history, "Rapper's Delight" by Sugarhill Gang (1979), reached 3rd place in the British singles chart. The channels through which rap gradually entered the United Kingdom were local pirate radio stations, national radio shows, as well as cassettes, mixtapes, and vinyl records brought by rap fans from the USA. At that time, British society was experiencing social turmoil, caused by the dissatisfaction of Britons with the victory of the Conservatives led by Margaret Thatcher. And when American films of the 1980s about hip-hop culture—"Wild Style," "Beat Street," "Message"—and the recordings of Grandmaster Flash & The Furious Five and the aforementioned "Planet Rock" reached Britain, the new style found fertile ground.

Just as in the USA, British hip-hop culture was started through street shows and parties. Here DJs would spin records, and MCs would perform live socially oriented lyrics. An important feature of British hip-hop was that it had a multinational and interracial character from the very beginning. This was due to the fact that different ethnic groups in the United Kingdom never lived in ghettos isolated in a way similar to those in the United States. That's why youth easily established cultural exchange. The 1980s became a fertile period for the music industry in the United Kingdom ("Christmas Rapping," Dizzy Heights, 1982; "London Bridge Is Falling Down," Newtrament, 1983; "Duck Rock" and "Buffalo Gals," Malcolm McLaren, "Beat Box," Art of Noise, 1983). Adam Ant and George Michael (Wham

and Captain Sensible) also entered rotation on major radio stations. A significant role in promoting hip-hop culture in the United Kingdom was played by the rap label "Street Sounds Record."

It is important to note a significant fact: British hip-hop, unlike American hip-hop, was developed under the influence of dub and toast. They were brought in by Jamaican migrants. British rappers began to mix elements of acid-house into their music. We can highlight some directions in original British hip-hop: 1) it includes those performers who work in the "club hip" style (Leftfield); 2) those who mix hip-hop and rave (Prodigy); 3) those who slowed down the hip-hop rhythm by adding acid-jazz, resulting in the emergence of trip-hop (Massive Attack). Overall, British hip-hop acquired a certain originality; distinctive subgenres and stylistic directions were developed. These aspects brought British hip-hop onto the global hip-hop culture scene, including the American one.

In the 2000s, "grime" was born in London — a genre of electronic dance music that mixed the then-trending electronic dance styles such as garage, jungle, and dubstep. The British scene also felt the influences of dancehall, ragga, reggae, and hip-hop. Aggressive rap delivery is a significant element of this genre. The lyrics written in its stream address urban-social themes — life in the big city. Over time, grime attracted attention from rappers from other countries (Skepta, Dizzee Rascal, Wiley, Kano, Lethal Bizzle). Grime crews also include: D Double E, Sway, Roll Deep, Tinie Tempah, Ghetts, Hadouken!, Virus Syndicate, Tinchy Stryder, Chase & Status. The revival of grime in 2014 was associated with the composition "German Whip" by Meridian Dan. Young British grime artists such as Stormzy, AJ Tracey, Novelist, Jammz, and Lady Leshurr are successfully making their way today. They are now actively in demand beyond the borders of the United Kingdom, including in the USA!

In 2005, Lady Sovereign achieved great success both in the United Kingdom and in America. This was facilitated by her meeting with American hip-hop performer and CEO of the labels Def Jam Recordings (also known as Def Jam, an American multinational record label owned by Universal Music Group; based in Manhattan, New York; primarily

specializing in hip-hop, contemporary R&B, soul, and pop music; the label has a London branch known as 0207 Def Jam; currently managed by EMI Records) and Roc-A-Fella Records Jay-Z (an American record label founded in 1994 by rapper Jay-Z, Damon "Dame" Dash, and Kareem "Biggs" Burke, and operating as a sublabel under Universal Music Group). Together with Usher and L.A. Reid, Jay-Z asked the singer to perform a freestyle. Lady Sovereign became the first non-American artist to sign to this label [Simon Price, 2007]. On October 31, 2006, her album *Public Warning* was released. Singles such as "Random," "9 to 5," "Hoodie," and "Love Me or Hate Me" were also released [Lady Sovereign: Official Site..., 2012; Lady Sovereign's Warning..., 2006]. Lady Sovereign's American tour began on October 23, 2006. Later, she appeared on *The Late Show with David Letterman*.

She also participated in tours with other artists, for example, Gwen Stefani's *The Sweet Escape Tour* in 2007. On October 17, 2006, the video for the song "Love Me or Hate Me" became the first by a British performer to reach number one on the American version of the MTV show *Total Request Live* [HMV.com: albums..., 2007]. After a conflict with Island Records, the singer announced on her website that the release of her album would take place on the independent label "Midget Records," with the release date set for April 7, 2009, in the USA and the United Kingdom. On December 8, 2009, Lady Sovereign announced the title of her album *Jigsaw*.

In the 2000s, with the emergence of new media platforms, such as online music streaming services, fans discovered hip-hop music by downloading or streaming it through social networks, starting with BlackPlanet and Myspace, as well as through YouTube, Worldstarhiphop, SoundCloud, and Spotify ["Hip-hop is the most listened to genre in the world...", 2016].

According to the U.S. Department of State, hip-hop "is now at the center of a mega music and fashion industry across the world," and this culture crosses social barriers, overcoming racial boundaries [Walker, Carol, 2006].

Regarding rap music — a component of hip-hop culture — it is noted that it has been an instrument for the political, social, and cultural expansion of its possibilities beyond

the USA. In particular, members of minority communities — such as Algerians in France and Turks in Germany — use rap as a platform to protest against racism, poverty, and unjust social structures ["Is hip hop driving the Arab Spring?", 2011].

Hip-hop culture was widely covered in the media, especially on television. In this regard, there were television shows dedicated to hip-hop, including in Europe (an example is "H.I.P. H.O.P.", 1984).

A vivid representative of European hip-hop is French hip-hop. Its path of evolution moved from imitation of the American tradition to the creation of its own identity. Hip-hop culture in France became popular among the international residents of the "les cités" — the French equivalents of American ghettos. Local DJs mainly played records by American artists and experimented with mixing their own compositions. Breakdancing also enjoyed great popularity among the youth. Radio played a significant role in the development of hip-hop: initially, rap could only be heard on small independent radio stations. Through them, the Afro-diaspora learned about Afrika Bambaataa, Run DMC, and Grandmaster Flash.

The birth of French hip-hop proper occurred at the turn of the 1980s and 1990s. Its founder was DJ Dee Nasty. At that time, he participated in American and regional DJ battles. In the second half of the 1980s, the first French rap groups emerged: NTM, Assassin, and Ministère A.M.E.R. They, in some ways, followed the creative path of Public Enemy and NWA. They created sharply social lyrics, criticizing authorities and discussing issues of racism, poverty, unemployment, and police brutality. At the beginning of the 1990s, a new trend was born in French hip-hop: rap became less political, more positive, even witty. In addition to the master MC Solaar, the French scene also featured: I Am, Saian Supa Crew, Mafia K-1 Fry, La Fonky Family, Ideal J, 3ème Œil, La Brigade. Local MCs began to write lyrics that more closely reflect the reality of their environment. Gradually, copying the American style faded away.

At the beginning of the 2000s, the general commercialization of hip-hop in the USA and the success of the new commercial "sound" forced French artists to turn their creative gaze across the ocean. The new generation of rappers (La Fouine and Rohff, Booba,

Kery James, Sinik) no longer copied their domestic predecessors. They returned to imitating the sound of their American colleagues. YouTube, Facebook, SoundCloud, and MySpace enabled the new generation of rap artists (Orelsan, 1.9.9.5, L'Entourage, Sexion d'Assaut, and Youssoupha) to loudly announce themselves to the whole world.

Polish hip-hop performers are well-known artists in Europe, especially in the Eastern Bloc. Many rappers from Poland collaborate with artists from Europe, the USA, and even Cuba.

Albanian hip-hop is one of the best-known in Europe. The term "Albanian hip-hop" also refers to other places populated by Albanians (diasporas), such as the USA, Germany, and the United Kingdom. Due to the 1992–1995 war, during which many sought refuge in other European countries and in the USA, many Bosnian and Herzegovinian hip-hop artists dispersed around the world, including the USA, Germany, Sweden, Austria, Denmark, the Netherlands, New Zealand, and others.

Mihail Stanislavov Mihaylov (Bulgarian: Михаил Станиславов Михайлов), 1972–, better known as Big Sha, is a Bulgarian rapper from Varna. Big Sha was featured in the song "Dime Piece" by LiLana along with American rapper Snoop Dogg. The song and video were released in Bulgaria on April 24, 2009. This was the first collaboration between a Bulgarian rapper and a globally renowned American rap star.

Important events in terms of the internationalization of hip-hop culture were hip-hop tours. Rap Tour Zine was the first international hip-hop tour in 1982. Its goal was to draw attention to the new European hip-hop culture. It united the contemporary elements of hip-hop at that time — MCs, DJs, B-boys, and graffiti artists. Among the most famous European hip-hop artists who have undertaken international tours, including to the USA, are: Suur Papa, Fowatile, Atlars, Get Open, King Size Terror, KOUSSEK, Suspect Packages, Yanigga, Freundeskreis, LEGEND JERRY, Põhja-Tallinn, Beebilõust, Droopy, Mic Fury, Rabasco, Pil C, 10-6, Lucas, S Curro, The Afeiliated, Soulslicers.

However, it must be acknowledged that they did not have a mass impact on the American hip-hop audience. In turn, hip-hop tours from the USA to Europe had a super influence on the European hip-hop audience; they brought multimillion-dollar profits both to the organizers of these tours and to the performers themselves. On some joint hip-hop tours, there was a full-fledged exchange of experience both in terms of performance and in terms of sharing ideas and themes. Mainly, this was a reaction to significant social events and specific social problems that concerned young people on both sides of the Atlantic — poverty, unemployment, social and societal marginalization of vulnerable youth, environmental issues, and the reference to the lives of the LGBT community, as well as to the evaluation and promotion of fashionable or influential subcultures. This particularly concerns the lives of diasporas in Europe, especially those from former European colonies — representatives of the Arab-Muslim population and African diasporas in Europe.

In our opinion, this theme strongly resonates with the history of the African population that was exported, particularly by slave owners from the southern United States. Today, African Americans make up 15% of the U.S. population, and they have an absolute influence on the development of hip-hop culture, exporting it to Europe. On the other hand, migrants from the Middle East and Africa began actively emigrating to Europe due to the weakening and collapse of the post-colonial system back in the 1970s. It is precisely this youth, among others, that produces examples of hip-hop culture in Europe, imported from the USA.

The most profitable hip-hop tour led by a woman was the coronation of Nicki Minaj as the new queen of hip-hop in 2015. *The Pinkprint Tour* demonstrated a flawless balance of dramatic Broadway theater, absurd fun, and the flexibility of artistic ferocity. Kendrick Lamar's tour in 2017–2018 presented populist anthems with the aim of stirring the masses. The album *Damned*, performed during his world tour, represented elevated rap. The tour opened with a martial arts film, a cheeky nod to Kendrick Lamar's kung-fu-style alter ego; then it transitioned into the breathtaking *DNA*. The giant tour of 2016 featured Drake, a superfan of the Toronto Raptors. Earlier, in 2015, tracks like *Jumpman* and *Big Rings* from his mixtape *What a Time to Be Alive* shook the global hip-hop scene. Kanye

West's tour in 2008 showed him as hungry, focused, and optimistic. Between 2002 and 2007, Young Money leader Lil Wayne released an astounding 16 mixtapes. In the *I Am Music Tour* (2008–2009), the majority of his 90-minute set was dedicated to *Tha Carter III* (2008). During the tour that took place in 2011–2012, hip-hop stars such as Jay-Z with his *Where I'm From* and West with his *Jesus Walks* performed from different stages located on opposite sides of the arena. The dream-team encore performance of the song *N—as in Paris* simply "blew up" the thousands of attendees.

Jazz hip-hop fusion represents a form of blending hip-hop beats, samples, scratching, and rap lyrics with jazz improvisation techniques. It became popular in the 1990s and continues to evolve in the 21st century thanks to the innovations of a new generation of jazz and hip-hop musicians. On the London club scene in the 1960s–1970s, DJs began mixing rare jazz compositions, mainly from the Blue Note catalog, with psychedelic styles, funk, and other popular genres, along with percussion tracks, aiming to achieve a groove (a syncopated and repetitive bass-and-drum-based foundation) — since then it has been called "acid jazz." In the 1980s, club DJs began adding hip-hop elements to the mix, emphasizing the rhythmic component, involving "live" musicians — drummers, percussionists, and horn players — who performed over pre-recorded music in order to create a new type of danceable jazz. At the same time in the USA, hip-hop DJs united with jazz artists to create a jazz-funk-hip-hop fusion style. For example, working with DJ Grand Mixer D.ST, jazz pianist Herbie Hancock experimented with the art of scratching in the hit *Rockit* (1983).

The fusion of jazz and hip-hop eventually became a distinctive style when rappers began sampling jazz melodies and rhythms from the records of Dizzy Gillespie, Lonnie Liston Smith, Donald Byrd, Sonny Rollins, Art Blakey, Roy Ayers, and others. In particular, Stetsasonic's *Talkin' All That Jazz* (In Full Gear, 1988) contains jazz break samples from Lonnie Liston Smith's *Expansions* and Donald Byrd's *Fallin' Like Dominoes*. Gang Starr was the first rap group to collaborate directly with jazz musicians, recording the song *Jazz Thing* with Branford Marsalis for Spike Lee's film *Mo' Better Blues* (1990) — it was imported from *Jazz Music* by Gang Starr (1989). However, it should be noted that most jazz musicians did not recognize the potential of rap for musical experimentation until 1990.

Saxophonist Greg Osby was the first to begin collaborating with rappers. As a result, he coined the term *Street Jazz* for this work. Working with Ali Shaheed Muhammad of A Tribe Called Quest and Eric Sadler from Public Enemy, Osby demonstrated the compatibility of the two idioms on *3-D Lifestyles* (1993). This album combines rap rhymes, hip-hop rhythms, scratching, R&B samples, and layered textures with jazz improvisations and lexicon. The commercial success of Osby's work led to similar collaborations between jazz musicians and rap, R&B, and pop artists. This, in turn, enriched hip-hop culture, especially in terms of collaboration between European and North American performers and producers.

In 1992, jazz musician Roy Ayers recorded *Double Trouble*, featuring funk vocalist Rick James and rap by Ayers. That same year, Miles Davis, under the direction of rap producer Easy Mo Bee, recorded *Doo-Bop*. *The Doo Bop Song* from this record includes samples from *Summer Madness* by the funk group Kool and the Gang. Rapper Guru from Gang Starr produced a session in 1993 with jazz musicians Roy Ayers, Donald Byrd, Ronnie Jordan, Courtney Pine, Lonnie Liston Smith, Gary Barnacle, Zachary Bro, Simon Low, Carlin Anderson, and N'Dea Davenport. As a result, the *Jazzmatazz* album emerged, an experimental fusion of hip-hop and jazz. That same year, Digable Planets recorded *Reachin' (A New Refutation of Time and Space)*. In 1994, Branford Marsalis recorded *Buckshot LeFonque*, an eclectic album that combined various popular styles with jazz. In particular, the track *The Scratch Opera* incorporates many techniques and elements of rap, such as sampling, scratching, rapping, and polytexturing.

At the beginning of the 1990s, hip-hop performers mainly rapped over looped jazz melody samples. However, by the late 1990s, jazz musicians began exploring new ways of synthesizing the languages of jazz and hip-hop. For example, trumpet player Russell Gunn in his album *Ethnomusicology* (1999) incorporated live instruments, improvisation, DJ scratching, and MC rap. Around the same time, jazz trumpeter Roy Hargrove started collaborating with the Soulquarians, a free collective of neo-soul and hip-hop performers, which also included Erykah Badu, Common, Questlove, and D'Angelo.

Hargrove appeared on influential albums executed in the neo-soul and hip-hop style, including *Like Water for Chocolate* by Common, *Mama's Gun* by Erykah Badu, and *Voodoo* by D'Angelo. Since then, this direction has begun incorporating elements of hip-hop and neo-soul into its own music, ultimately leading to the creation of the hip-hop-soul-jazz fusion group *The RH Factor* in the early 2000s. These works eventually came to define the trajectory of jazz and hip-hop fusion at the beginning of the 21st century. The RH Factor released their debut album, *Hard Groove*, in 2003. On this groundbreaking record, fellow Soulquarians collaborators Erykah Badu, Common, and D'Angelo joined Hargrove.

Overall, the innovative blend of jazz, hip-hop, and contemporary rhythm and blues by RH Factor had a significant influence on young musicians, particularly Robert Glasper and Snarky Puppy, who mastered jazz improvisation while maintaining close ties to other styles of African American music, including hip-hop, soul, and contemporary gospel. Along with *Hard Groove*, another significant influence on the development of jazz-hip-hop fusion in the early 2000s came from alternative hip-hop producer James "J Dilla" Yancey. His unique production style was marked by complex combinations of short samples — often borrowed from classic jazz recordings. He frequently used a drum machine to manually execute his beats. This process gave his beats a sense of freedom and flexibility, which in turn caught the attention of drummers both in hip-hop and jazz. This is a testament to the creative unification of different musical directions, significantly enriching the modern musical performance palette and developing, above all, the fusion culture of contemporary hip-hop.

After the contributions of Hargrove and Dilla, the next fifteen years saw a wave of important jazz hip-hop fusion records, during which the language of hip-hop became more deeply rooted in the work of young jazz musicians. Pianist Robert Glasper was one of the most influential representatives of the next generation. He toured with *The RH Factor*, witnessing the impact of J. Dilla on his own work. A key contribution of Glasper's was the adaptation of characteristic hip-hop rhythms and cycles to the instruments of a jazz piano trio. Glasper continued this path, creating *Robert Glasper Experiment*, whose jazz-hip-hop fusion album *Black Radio* (2012) won a Grammy for Best R&B Album.

The 2010s became the stage for jazz and hip-hop fusion projects. Chicago jazz trumpeter Marquis Hill, who won the prestigious Thelonious Monk Jazz Trumpet competition in 2014, mentioned Robert Glasper in terms of his unique understanding of post-bop jazz improvisation and alternative hip-hop. In general, it should be noted that the lyrics associated with jazz-hip-hop fusion cover a wide range of social themes. They varied from topics of romance, life experiences, and world events to social commentary on the historical past, conditions of poverty, and other issues that have negatively affected the lives of African Americans – both in the United States and in continental Europe.

Ukrainian hip-hop is a key part of the Ukrainian music scene. It pertains to all genres of hip-hop music performed in the Ukrainian language. The term "ukr-hop" is also sometimes used to refer to any hip-hop music created by Ukrainians, including instrumental hip-hop as well as rap songs by representatives of the Ukrainian diaspora.

In Ukraine, hip-hop was introduced in the 1990s. In 1989, TNMK and V.U.Z.V. emerged on the hip-hop scene. In the late 1990s – early 2000s, Kharkiv and Lviv were considered the main centers of the Ukrainian hip-hop subculture. Many bands performed successfully at the "Chervona Ruta" and "Tavriiski Igry" festivals. In the mid-2000s, many underground bands and performers from other cities of Ukraine appeared and gained popularity: DaHok (Drohobych), Zakhidna Koalitsiya (Stryi), Kryzhik (Uman), Sheksta (Stryi), Sirius MC (Kalush), and Freel (Kyiv). In 2005, the song "Razom nas bahato" by the group GreenJolly became the unofficial anthem of the Orange Revolution. In 2008, the hip-hop group LEZO released their 4th studio album "Hostroslovy." In the same year, KyLЯ and RYLEZ created the band "Tulym" – one of the most popular Ukrainian boom-bap bands. **On March 11, 2011, Ukrainian rapper Ivan Buyan presented his first video clip filmed in New York.** On June 19, 2014, PVNCH presented their new album *Holodnyi* (Ukr. *Hungry*). As a result of voting, it was recognized as the best hip-hop album of 2014. On April 18, 2015, the Kyiv band "Tulym" held a concert with the legendary New York hip-hop group Onyx in Sofia (Bulgaria).

An important note: in terms of styles, domestic hip-hop is heavily influenced by Jamaican reggae and Ukrainian folk music. As a result, this leads to a wonderful melodic and soft sound. Also, Ukraine has seen an increase in immigrants from West Africa. Consequently, hip-hop events reflect musical trends that are popular in West Africa [Helbig, Adriana, 2014].

The most successful hip-hop artist of today is Kendrick Lamar. He performed with Snoop Dogg, Dr. Dre, Mary J. Blige, and other hip-hop stars during the Super Bowl session in 2022. At that time, he released his fifth studio album *Mr. Morale & the Big Steppers*. The 18-track album, created in collaboration with various musicians, is noted for its complexity and self-reflection; it won a Grammy for Best Rap Album, Rap Song, and Rap Performance. In November 2024, K. Lamar released *GNX*, a 12-track album. Despite mixed reviews, fans eagerly awaited his appearance at the 2025 Super Bowl show, where the Philadelphia Eagles dominated the Kansas City Chiefs with a final score of 22-40. He performed for the first time as the headliner at this event. On stage, Lamar was joined by his frequent collaborator SZA, as well as unexpected guests Samuel L. Jackson and Serena Williams.

In the 2020s, some of the early icons of hip-hop – LL Cool J, Ice Cube, Queen Latifah, Ice-T – also established themselves as familiar faces in film and television. Snoop Dogg headlined rock festivals alongside Bruce Springsteen and appeared in TV shows with lifestyle guru Martha Stewart. In the 2010s, hip-hop found its niche on the internet. The file-sharing and media streaming service SoundCloud allowed musicians of all types to upload and promote tracks, bypassing traditional distribution channels. SoundCloud rappers developed their own sound and subculture. SoundCloud rappers Lil Uzi Vert and Post Malone achieved massive success in the mainstream. **Post Malone's track "Sunflower" became one of the best-selling singles of all time.** Cardi B gained a large following on social media platforms like Vine and Instagram. In 2019, she became the first solo female rapper to win a Grammy for Best Rap Album with *Invasion of Privacy*. *Old Town Road* in 2022 received a "17-times Platinum" certification from the Recording Industry Association of America (RIAA).

Creating lyrics with a strong London accent, Stormzy gained widespread critical recognition; in 2019, he became the first British rapper to headline the Glastonbury Festival. He later launched #Merky Books, a Penguin Random House imprint focusing on the British African diaspora. On January 20, 2025, Nelly, Snoop Dogg, Rick Ross, and Soulja Boy performed at the inauguration ball for President Donald Trump [Cain, Sian. "This isn't politics: Nelly defends decision to perform at Trump inauguration ball after backlash". *The Guardian*. January 20, 2025]. On February 22, 2025, the 56th NAACP Image Awards ceremony took place. Doechii was named Best New Artist. Kendrick Lamar received awards for Best Hip-Hop/Rap Song and Best Music Video/Visual Album for his song *Not Like Us* [Smart, Jack; Walcott, Escher. "NAACP Image Awards 2025: See the Complete Winners List". *People*. February 23, 2025].

Conclusions.

International connections in hip-hop culture are sustained through many forms, including tours, joint battles, and recordings at leading studios on both sides of the Atlantic. Another avenue for promoting hip-hop culture in North American and other regions is the participation of diaspora representatives in Europe (Africans, people from Turkey and the Balkans, etc.). These contacts share the common origins of hip-hop – from Africa, Mesoamerica, and so on. The international nature of hip-hop culture is also enriched by influences from other directions and branches of hip-hop culture – from rap to techno, industrial, and electropop. Thus, the vibrant palette of hip-hop culture is constantly enriched with new elements and motifs from Central and Southern Europe. Central to their structure are motifs originating from France and the United Kingdom. Another important factor in the widespread dissemination of hip-hop culture is the common use of modern equipment for performing hip-hop compositions, such as MC stations, digital setups, etc.

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